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DEVELOPMENT OF A VIRTUAL CHARACTER WALKING SIMULATOR USING REINFORCEMENT LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

A reproducible reinforcement learning pipeline using joystick control for humanoid locomotion of the Unitree G1 in MuJoCo Playground is provided. PPO training is performed on flat terrain for 200M simulation steps and evaluation is conducted via fixed-energy penalization, recovery-aware regularization, zero-shot transfer to rough terrain, and sim-to-sim PyBullet execution. Ablations on fixed energy penalties show that $\lambda E = -0.001$ is the only relevant trainable setting amongst all tested penalties, thus, chosen as the fixed baseline for comparison with other methods. It can be observed that fixed-energy penalty decreases energy consumption but at the expense of robustness and gait consistency of humanoid locomotion, while the proposed recovery-aware regularization ensures a more stable walking pattern and better gait structure on flat terrain and under zero-shot terrain transfer. The evaluation is supported by various physical metrics and gait diagnostics of humanoid movement, including torso height trajectories, XY paths, and foot-contact patterns. Cross-simulator executability is found to be not sufficient for stability through a PyBullet sim-to-sim evaluation, highlighting the significance of execution within the context of policy deployment for humanoid walking tasks.

Keywords: Reinforcement learning, humanoid locomotion, Unitree G1, MuJoCo Playground, Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO), fixed-energy penalization, recovery-aware regularization, zero-shot terrain transfer, gait diagnostics, sim-to-sim transfer, PyBullet.

Introduction

Humanoid locomotion is one of the central problems in robotics because it is directly related to the development of general-purpose robots capable of operating in human environments. At the same time, stable humanoid walking remains difficult due to high-dimensional whole-body dynamics, intermittent contact events, and sensitivity to terrain and external disturbances. Recent progress in deep reinforcement learning has shown that massively parallel training can substantially accelerate locomotion learning and produce effective walking controllers for legged systems [1]. In addition, recent real-world studies have demonstrated that reinforcement learning can generate robust humanoid locomotion policies beyond simplified laboratory settings [2]. More recent work has further shown that learned humanoid locomotion can be extended to challenging terrain conditions, highlighting the importance of robustness under environmental variation [3]. Within this broader area, reproducible simulation pipelines have become increasingly important for training and evaluating locomotion controllers. High-throughput simulation frameworks such as Brax have made it possible to scale policy learning through parallel rollouts [4], while GPU-based platforms such as Isaac Gym have further emphasized the value of fast simulation for robot learning [5]. In the MuJoCo ecosystem, MuJoCo Playground provides standardized locomotion tasks and an end-to-end workflow for training, evaluation, and deployment-oriented experimentation on humanoid robots [6]. HumanoidBench emphasizes the need for standardized evaluations over various tasks related to humanoid locomotion and manipulation, where a simple average over performance measures may not be enough to represent successes, failure modes, or the

inherent complexity of body movement [7]. Despite this progress, several important questions remain open. A policy that performs well on flat terrain may still degrade substantially under domain shift, and methods based on domain randomization or rapid adaptation indicate that robust transfer requires explicit evaluation under changing conditions [8,9]. In addition, locomotion quality cannot be judged only by reward, because stable policies may still require excessive actuation effort. For this reason, physical measures such as energy, power, traveled distance, and cost of transport are necessary for analyzing the trade-off between robustness and efficiency [10,11]. Moreover, the use of fixed-penalties on energy might lead to a serious contradiction since more significant penalization might lower the amount of actuation needed, while at the same time preventing the necessary correction to ensure the stability of the humanoid locomotion. Therefore, the idea of energy regularization conditioned by stability becomes necessary. Finally, even when a controller performs well in one simulator, it may fail in another due to differences in contact dynamics, friction modeling, or actuation behavior. Sim-to-sim validation in environments such as PyBullet is therefore an important step for deployment-oriented analysis [12]. In this study, a reproducible simulator of joystick-controlled humanoid walking on the Unitree G1 in MuJoCo Playground is presented, and the resulting locomotion policy is validated using the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [13]. Training of flat terrain walking policies are done using 200M environment steps for three random seeds, with the robustness of the policy being validated using zero-shot transfer to rough terrain. An ablation study is performed by varying fixed-penalty terms to determine a sensible value for the baseline. This analysis forms

the basis for proposing a new recovery-aware regularization for the problem where the energy penalty term is determined based on the current stability of the humanoid. The various policies obtained from the experiments are compared based on robustness criteria, physical efficiency metrics, and gait diagnostics, namely, torso height trajectories, XY paths, and foot contacts. Finally, the trained policies, configurations, and actuator metadata are adapted for the sim-to-sim transfers in Py-Bullet.

Related Work

Recent survey studies have reviewed the most important aspects and problems associated with robotic reinforcement learning. Tang, Abbatematteo, Hu, Chandra, Mart'ın-Mart'ın, and Stone [14] have investigated successful examples of using deep reinforcement learning in robots and analyzed important problems related to observation design, reward formulation, evaluation, and application to dynamic environments. The paper is relevant to the current work in the sense that locomotion policy evaluation should account not only for the obtained reward but also for robustness, reproducibility, and experimental comparability. Energy-aware locomotion has become one of the most important directions in legged-robot learning. Vu, Lai, and Liu [15] explored walking gaits based on the principles of passive dynamics, taking into account efficiency criteria such as the cost of transport. This research inspires adding energy-related metrics to those used in robotic reinforcement learning. The potential of using energy regularization as an explicit target to influence the locomotion behavior has been studied. The work of Sferrazza, Huang, Lin, Lee, and Abbeel [7] has shown that energy-regularization can be used to achieve natural gait patterns in legged robots. Fu, Kumar, Malik, and Pathak [10] proposed an adaptive energy-regularization scheme for quadruped locomotion, which showed that energy-based reward design could promote gait transition while increasing their efficiency. However, none of these studies explicitly differentiate between the stable and unstable locomotion stages. In contrast, in the current study, a new recovery-aware energy regularization is considered for humanoid locomotion, including energy-based penalties during stable walking and no penalty during unstable walking. In recent studies, the field of humanoid control was also considered in terms of advanced policy frameworks and learning techniques. Gu, Wang, Zhu, Shi, Guo, Liu, and Chen [16] introduced Denoising World Model Learning (DWL), a novel end-to-end reinforcement learning approach for humanoid locomotion over challenging terrains. This method uses a world-model learned world-model in the training process and shows zero-shot transfer capability from sim-to-real on snowy, inclined, stair, and uneven terrains. Lobos-Tsunekawa, Leiva, and Ruiz-del-Solar [17] have introduced a model that uses vision-based navigation for a humanoid biped robot, which uses deep reinforcement learning where the visual data acquired from color images help generate the motion commands. This research study has relevance due to its application of vision-based control beyond mere proprioceptive movements in a humanoid. Gu, Li, Shen, Yu, Xie, McCrory, Cheng,

Shamsah, Griffin, Liu, Kheddar, Peng, Zhu, Shi, Nguyen, Cheng, Gao, and Zhao [18] reviewed current developments and issues in the areas of humanoid locomotion and manipulation, especially in terms of control, planning, and learning techniques. The review finds that there is a shift in humanoid robotics research from pure walking to integrated approaches that combine locomotion, manipulation, and overall whole-body motion of the robot. Humanoid control oriented towards recovery has also garnered more interest recently. He, Dong, Chen, and Gupta [19] suggested HUMANUP, which is a two-stage framework for acquiring learning-based control of getting up and rolling over skills for the Unitree G1 humanoid robot in various postures and terrains through reinforcement learning. The contributions by the authors emphasize the significance of a carefully designed curriculum, posture randomization, and deployment-oriented regularization for contact-intensive recovery tasks. He [20] introduced ASAP, a methodology for matching the dynamics of virtual and real-world humanoids for agile whole-body behavior. This research is relevant to the current study since it demonstrates the necessity of having the same control interface, which is not enough when the physical models in the simulation environment differ from real world. As a control-oriented baseline, Ma, Zhao, Kolathaya, and Ames [21] presented a unified PD and impedance control framework for human-like bipedal locomotion, proving to be superior to the sole use of PD control. Together, these works show the progress made towards developing humanoid control algorithms with scalability, transferability, and physical consistency. However, fewer works provide an all-in-one approach for the integration of training humanoid locomotion using PPO on flat terrain, fixed-penalty ablation, recovery-aware energy regularization, zero-shot transfer to rough terrain, gait-diagnostic analysis. This paper fills this void by providing a unified experimental pipeline.

Methodology

Problem formulation and control objective.

The joystick-controlled humanoid locomotion task is formulated as a Markov decision process (MDP):

$$\mathcal{M} = (\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, p, r, \gamma). \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{S} denotes the state space, \mathcal{A} denotes the action space, p is the transition dynamics, r is the reward function, and γ is the discount factor.

At each control step, the policy receives an observation o_t , selects an action a_t according to $\pi_\theta(a_t | o_t)$, and receives a reward r_t after the simulator is advanced. The learning objective is to maximize the expected discounted return:

$$J(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{\pi_\theta} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{T-1} \gamma^t r_t \right]. \quad (2)$$

where $J(\theta)$ is the expected return, θ denotes the policy parameters, T is the episode horizon, γ is the discount factor, and r_t is the reward at time step t .

Simulation environments and task definition (MuJoCo Playground). The proposed work uses the MuJoCo Playground environments for the Unitree G1 humanoid robot [6]. Two environments are considered: Flat terrain, which is used as the training domain, and

Rough terrain, which is used as the domain-shift evaluation domain. Each episode has a horizon of $T = 1000$ control steps. The simulator uses a physics time step of $\Delta t_{\text{sim}} = 0.002$ s and a control time step of $\Delta t_{\text{ctrl}} = 0.02$ s. Therefore, the number of physics steps per control step is

$$N = \frac{\Delta t_{\text{ctrl}}}{\Delta t_{\text{sim}}}. \quad (3)$$

where N is the number of physics simulation steps executed during one policy control step.

The joystick command is defined as $c_t = [v_x, v_y, \omega_z]$ and is bounded by the limits specified in the task configuration:

$$v_x \in [-1, 1], \quad v_y \in [-0.5, 0.5], \quad \omega_z \in [-1, 1]. \quad (4)$$

where v_x is the forward velocity command, v_y is the lateral velocity command, and ω_z is the yaw-rate command.

The simulation and integration of the MuJoCo environment follow the standard MuJoCo computation model [22]. The official randomization and noise settings are retained to support generalization and reduce overfitting to a single simulator configuration [8, 23].

Observations, actions, and low-level actuation.

The policy input is a state-like observation vector that contains base orientation features, base linear and angular velocities, joint positions and velocities, the current joystick command, and the previous action. A compact notation is

$$o_t = [\hat{g}_t, v_t, \omega_t, q_t, \dot{q}_t, c_t, a_{t-1}]. \quad (5)$$

where \hat{g}_t denotes projected gravity or an equivalent base-orientation feature, v_t and ω_t denote the base linear and angular velocities, q_t and \dot{q}_t denote joint positions and joint velocities, c_t is the joystick command, and a_{t-1} is the previous action. The policy action is a continuous normalized vector:

$$a_t \in [-1, 1]^n. \quad (6)$$

where n is the number of actuated degrees of freedom.

The normalized action is converted into desired joint targets relative to a nominal pose. The low-level PD-like actuation is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} q_t^{\text{des}} &= q_{\text{nom}} + \kappa_a a_t, & \tau_t \\ &= K_p (q_t^{\text{des}} - q_t) - K_d \dot{q}_t. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where q_t^{des} is the desired joint-position target, q_{nom} is the nominal joint configuration, κ_a is the action-scaling coefficient, a_t is the normalized action, τ_t is the commanded joint torque, K_p and K_d are proportional and derivative gains, and \dot{q}_t is the joint-velocity vector.

Learning algorithm and baseline training configuration. The policies are trained using Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [13]. PPO uses the probability ratio

$$\rho_t(\theta) = \frac{\pi_\theta(a_t | o_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}(a_t | o_t)}. \quad (8)$$

where π_θ is the updated policy, $\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}$ is the previous policy, a_t is the action, and o_t is the observation. The clipped PPO surrogate objective is

$$\mathcal{L}^{\text{CLIP}}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_t [\min(\rho_t(\theta) \hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(\rho_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) \hat{A}_t)]. \quad (9)$$

where \hat{A}_t is the advantage estimate and ϵ is the clipping parameter. In the baseline configuration, $\epsilon = 0.2$.

The training process follows the official MuJoCo Playground/Brax configuration. The policy and value function use a feedforward multilayer perceptron (MLP) with hidden layer sizes (512, 256, 128). The baseline PPO configuration uses a discount factor of $\gamma = 0.95$, learning rate 3×10^{-4} , clipping parameter 0.2, entropy coefficient 0.005, unroll length 20, and 8192 parallel environments. Flat-terrain training is performed for 200 M environment steps using three random seeds. This setup provides learning curves and checkpoints for reproducibility analysis.

Reward design and energy regularization ablation. The environment reward follows the official MuJoCo Playground task design and consists of weighted components such as command tracking, stability and orientation shaping, contact and slip terms, joint-deviation terms, and termination-related terms. The task reward can be written as

$$r_t^{\text{task}} = \sum_{i=1}^K w_i r_t^{(i)}. \quad (10)$$

where $r_t^{(i)}$ denotes the i -th reward component, w_i is the corresponding weight, and K is the number of reward terms.

To study the robustness-efficiency trade-off, an energy-regularization term is added to the task reward:

$$r_t = r_t^{\text{task}} + \lambda_E E_t. \quad (11)$$

where r_t is the final reward at time step t , r_t^{task} is the task reward, E_t is an energy- or effort-related quantity obtained from the simulator, and λ_E is the energy-regularization coefficient. The no-penalty setting corresponds to $\lambda_E = 0$, while negative values of λ_E penalize energy use more strongly. Because changing λ_E directly changes the scale of the return, the analysis emphasizes robustness and efficiency metrics in addition to return.

Recovery-aware energy regularization. To avoid applying the same energy penalty at every time step, a recovery-aware regularization mechanism is introduced. Instead of using a constant penalty coefficient during the entire episode, the effective energy coefficient is modulated according to the current stability state of the humanoid:

$$\lambda_E^{\text{eff}}(t) = \lambda_0 \cdot \mathbb{I}[\text{stable}(t)]. \quad (12)$$

where $\lambda_E^{\text{eff}}(t)$ is the effective energy-regularization coefficient at time step t , λ_0 is the nominal recovery-aware penalty weight, and $\mathbb{I}[\cdot]$ is the indicator function that equals one when the stability condition is satisfied and zero otherwise.

The stability condition is defined using torso orientation and base angular velocity:

$$\text{stable}(t) = (\text{tilt}(t) < \theta_{\text{tilt}}) \wedge (\|\omega_t\| < \theta_\omega). \quad (13)$$

where $\text{tilt}(t)$ is the magnitude of the horizontal component of the projected gravity vector, ω_t is the base angular velocity, θ_{tilt} is the torso-tilt threshold, and θ_ω is the angular-velocity threshold. In the present experiments, $\theta_{\text{tilt}} = 0.5$ rad and $\theta_\omega = 1.0$ rad/s were used.

The final reward with recovery-aware regularization is

$$r_t = r_t^{\text{task}} + \lambda_E^{\text{eff}}(t)E_t. \quad (14)$$

where r_t is the final reward at time step t , r_t^{task} is the original task reward, $\lambda_E^{\text{eff}}(t)$ is the stability-conditioned energy coefficient, and E_t is the energy- or effort-related term. When the robot is unstable, $\lambda_E^{\text{eff}}(t) = 0$, so the energy penalty is removed and the policy can use stronger corrective actions to recover balance. When the robot is stable, $\lambda_E^{\text{eff}}(t) = \lambda_0$, so energy regularization is reactivated to encourage more efficient locomotion.

In this study, the recovery-aware mechanism is compared with the no-penalty baseline and the fixed-penalty policy with $\lambda_E = -0.001$. Unlike the fixed-penalty policy, the recovery-aware design does not aim to minimize energy at every time step. Instead, it relaxes the energy penalty during unstable phases so that the policy can use corrective actions for balance recovery, while reactivating the penalty during stable walking.

Experimental protocol: flat training and zero-shot transfer. The experimental protocol is aligned with the reported results and consists of two main stages:

- **Flat training.** PPO is trained on Flat terrain for 200 M environment steps using three random seeds.
- **Zero-shot transfer.** The flat-trained policy is evaluated on Rough terrain without parameter updates in order to test out-of-domain generalization under a controlled terrain shift.

This protocol follows common transfer-evaluation practice in locomotion reinforcement learning, where terrain changes are used as a stress test for robustness [3, 8, 9].

Evaluation metrics and gait diagnostics. Metrics are collected over evaluation rollouts and aggregated across episodes or seeds where applicable. Robustness metrics include survival length, success rate, episode return, and termination-related indicators. The success rate is defined as

$$\text{SR} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=1}^M \mathbb{I}(L_k = T). \quad (15)$$

where SR is the success rate, M is the number of evaluated episodes, $\mathbb{I}(\cdot)$ is the indicator function, L_k is the survival length (steps alive) of episode k , and T is the episode horizon.

Energy and efficiency metrics include total energy, mean power, traveled distance, and cost of transport (CoT):

$$d = \|p_T^{xy} - p_0^{xy}\|_2, \quad \text{CoT} = \frac{E_{\text{ep}}}{mgd}. \quad (16)$$

where d is the horizontal displacement, p_0^{xy} and p_T^{xy} are the initial and final torso positions projected onto the horizontal plane, E_{ep} is the episode energy, m is the robot mass, and g is the gravitational acceleration.

In addition to scalar metrics, gait diagnostics include torso-height trajectories $z(t)$, XY position traces, and foot-contact or air-time patterns. These diagnostics help reveal failure modes such as collapse, drift, and irregular contact timing that may not be fully captured by aggregate scores.

Hyperparameter sensitivity tests. Short flat-terrain sensitivity experiments are conducted to examine the effects of learning rate, discount factor, and network size without repeating the full 200 M-step training budget for every setting. The learning-rate and discount-factor sweeps are performed for 20 M steps under a fixed evaluation schedule. These experiments serve as control checks to verify that the selected baseline is reasonable and that the main findings are not driven by an obviously poor hyperparameter choice.

Artifact packaging for sim-to-sim transfer. To support future sim-to-sim experiments, the trained policy and associated metadata are packaged into a reproducible artifact set. This package includes policy parameters, observation-normalization information where applicable, environment configuration files, PPO configuration files, evaluation CSV files, checkpoint folders, and actuator metadata.

Results

In this section, the results of experiments related to the proposed energy-regularization framework are presented. The analysis starts by explaining the rationale behind choosing $\lambda_E = -0.001$ as the baseline fixed-penalty through a fixed-penalty ablation study. Then, the performance of the no-penalty, fixed-penalty, and recovery-aware approaches is compared on flat terrain based on learning dynamics, robustness, energy-efficiency metrics, and gait diagnostics. Finally, the transfer of zero-shot capability to rough terrain and sim-to-sim performance in PyBullet are evaluated. Before the main comparison, three weights of fixed-energy penalty were considered in the case of flat terrain. The learning process and robustness results for $\lambda_E = -0.001$, $\lambda_E = -0.005$, and $\lambda_E = -0.01$ are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Energy penalty ablation

The effect of the fixed-penalty ablation is shown for flat terrain, using three different penalty strengths, such as $\lambda_E = -0.001$, -0.005 , and -0.01 . For all three cases, the learning starts with roughly the same starting values of the reward; however, their dynamics are significantly different during the training course. The weakest penalty $\lambda_E = -0.001$ is the only configuration where the reward increases steadily and results in an increased final reward value. The stronger penalties $\lambda_E = -0.005$ and $\lambda_E = -0.01$ do not improve during the learning course and result in low or negative values of the reward, meaning that such policies cannot learn to walk stably due to too strong penalties. Therefore, these plots demonstrate that larger fixed-penalties limit the learning itself by preventing further improvement, rather than changing the final energy configuration. For this reason, $\lambda_E = -0.001$ was chosen as the baseline for fixed-penalties. The robustness comparison for the three fixed-penalty cases in terms of success rate, average survival length, and return is presented. This is

again consistent with the results in the learning curves. The mild penalty weight $\lambda_E = -0.001$ still stands out as the most robust choice, yielding positive success rate, longer survival, and higher return in comparison with the two heavier penalty schemes. On the other hand, the two heavier penalty schemes are almost equivalent to failure in the sense that their success rates and episode survival lengths are close to zero. The conclusion drawn from this analysis is that the decline in learning curves is caused by something beyond reward scaling: the heavier penalties also result in much poorer stability in locomotion. Figures A and B provide support for using $\lambda_E = -0.001$ as the fixed-penalty baseline.

After selecting $\lambda_E = -0.001$ as the fixed-penalty weight, the main experiment was conducted under the conditions of flat terrain. Learning dynamics for all approaches in terms of 200M environment steps are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Learning curves on flat terrain

In all cases, the learning curve demonstrates considerable progress until reaching the 200M step limit, meaning that all three setups remain trainable. Nonetheless, the learning curve differs significantly: the recovery-aware learning curve increases its growth rate after the initial period and stays above the two other conditions during almost all training stages, while achieving the highest score by the end of training. On the other hand, the no-penalty learning curve achieves stable learning performance and approaches the second-highest achieved reward, with the fixed-penalty

setup achieving slower improvement and staying below both other conditions during the last half of training. At the end of training, the learning curve for the recovery-aware learning reaches around 15–16 mean evaluation rewards, with the no-penalty curve being closer to 12–13, and the fixed-penalty learning curve achieving around 9.

Before comparing the learning dynamics quantitatively, rollout screenshots were used as an evidence of testing all policies under the required simulation configuration shown in Figure 3.

Flat terrain

Rough terrain

Figure 3: Unitree G1 screenshots: Flat and Rough

These screenshots show that the Unitree G1 robot's body morphology does not change when moving from one environment to another, although the condition of the terrain changes from flat to rough. Such findings prove the assumption that the differences in robot locomotion can be attributed to the change in the terrain

and not to the modifications made to the robot morphology.

Tables 1 and 2 compare three types of policy in terms of no-penalty, fixed-penalty (with $\lambda E = -0.001$), and recovery-aware control policies, tested under conditions of flat terrain and zero-shot transfer to rough terrain.

Table 1

Flat-terrain comparison.

Category	Metric	No penalty	-0.001 penalty	Recovery-aware
Robustness	Success rate (SR)	75.0%	50.0%	60.0%
Robustness	Steps alive	906.00 ± 225.61	726.40 ± 324.14	851.80 ± 216.94
Robustness	Return sum	27.48 ± 8.51	23.30 ± 12.34	21.96 ± 8.02
Gait quality	feet air time	0.0771	0.0765	0.0744
Gait quality	feet air time/var	0.0027	0.0035	0.0026
Gait quality	feet slip	0.2472	0.2138	0.1110
Gait quality	swing peak	0.0629	0.0435	0.0538

Table 2

Zero-shot rough-terrain comparison.

Category	Metric	No penalty	-0.001 penalty	Recovery-aware
Robustness	Success rate (SR)	30.0%	10.0%	20.0%
Robustness	Steps alive	715.65 ± 291.61	443.00 ± 285.79	603.80 ± 329.02
Robustness	Return sum	13.09 ± 11.52	7.38 ± 7.94	10.05

Table 1 summarizes the results of comparisons between the no-penalty, the fixed-penalty policy with the coefficient for penalties $\lambda E = -0.001$, and the proposed recovery-aware policy on the basis of flat terrain in relation to their robustness and gait quality. The no-penalty demonstrates the highest robustness, although the fixed-penalty policy allows one to train the neural network policy and still provides weaker stability and survival. Moreover, recovery-aware penalty partially brings robustness indicators back. In particular, conditioning the penalty on stability is better than applying a uniform penalty in every time step. As for the gait quality, recovery-aware penalties bring higher repeatability and lower slip and airtime variability, which means more repetitive contacts. Thus, the results confirm the previous conclusion that a uniform penalty decreases stability and gait quality. Table 2 shows the zero-shot rough-terrain comparison for the no-penalty, fixed-penalty with $\lambda E = -0.001$, and recovery-aware policies. The no-penalty still stands as the most robust setting in

the transfer process. However, the fixed-penalty significantly affects the zero-shot performance and makes the robot survive a shorter time under the change in terrain. In comparison, the recovery-aware policy can somewhat recover from the loss of robustness when compared with the fixed-penalty policy, showing that using stability as the condition for penalization is more robust under out-of-domain conditions than using the fixed-penalty approach. In conclusion, zero-shot analysis shows that the fixed-penalty reduces the robot's capacity to deal with rough-terrain disturbances, whereas recovery-aware regularization maintains robustness in transfer performance.

In order to verify whether lower energy consumption results in better locomotion, four physical efficiency metrics were evaluated under the conditions of flat terrain. These include mean power, total energy, distance traveled, and the cost of transport shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Energy panel

For all of them, the statistics were calculated for $n = 10$ evaluated episodes. In particular, the no-penalty resulted in 130.33 ± 29.69 W mean power, 2352.16 ± 824.92 J total energy, 5.06 ± 3.10 m traveled distance, and 1.99 ± 1.50 CoT. The application of a fixed-penalty $\lambda E = -0.001$ reduced the mean power and total energy to 91.44 ± 27.44 W and 1409.68 ± 778.24 J, respectively; however, this penalty resulted in reducing the traveled distance to 3.40 ± 3.02 m and increased CoT to 2.40 ± 3.38 . The recovery-aware policy had higher energy consumption, namely, 180.39 ± 35.71 W mean power and 3079.91 ± 1067.04 J total energy, along with 4.45

± 2.53 m traveled distance and 3.44 ± 3.91 CoT. Overall, it can be stated that the fixed-penalty leads to lower energy consumption, however, to a certain extent at the expense of reducing locomotion, while recovery-aware regularization enables greater continuity of motion through reduction of the penalty applied during times of instability.

In addition to scalar metrics, trajectory-based analysis was used to study the policy development throughout execution. Figure 5 shows the comparison of the XY paths of the torso for the no-penalty, fixed-penalty, and recovery-aware policies.

Figure 5: XY paths

The XY paths on flat terrain offer further clarity regarding stability and directional consistency in locomotion. The no-penalty policy yields a continuous and elongated path, implying that there was constant forward movement throughout the episode. The fixed-penalty policy with $\lambda E = -0.001$ produces a shorter and

more concentrated trajectory, meaning that there is a lesser extent of progression and less efficient locomotion despite producing an almost linear path. Finally, the policy that takes into account recovery generates a similar path to the base policy in terms of length and continuity but is more stable compared to the fixed-

penalty policy. Despite the corrections observed in the trajectory, they appear to be within the acceptable range of movement without compromising balance. Overall, the XY-paths analysis shows that the findings obtained through the use of quantitative methods are consistent;

in particular, the fixed-penalty causes poor effectiveness of locomotion compared to recovery-aware regularization. In order to evaluate the level of postural stability, the torso height was tracked at each control step. Figure 6 demonstrates the vertical position of the torso $z(t)$ for the three policies.

Figure 6: Torso height $z(t)$

The torso-height trajectories on flat terrain reveal differences in the long-term locomotion stability among the three policies. The torso height of no-penalty policy remains almost unchanged, reaching a value of about $z \approx 0.80$ m throughout the whole trajectory. Thus, the robot manages to maintain a relatively stable posture and walk without falling down at all during the 1000-step rollout. In the case of the fixed-penalty policy for $\lambda E = -0.001$, the height of the torso remains unchanged initially, but it starts dropping sharply after about 300 steps, reaching almost zero values by step

400. This suggests that the robot falls down earlier than expected due to the deterioration of its posture stability. The recovery-aware method retains a relatively consistent torso height near the original level throughout the entire episode without any major local deviation or falling incident. From the findings above, the fixed-penalty method fails to promote stability, while the recovery-aware approach is more successful. Figure 7 shows the comparison of the left and right foot contacts for the three walking policies on the flat terrain.

Figure 7: Foot contact

Clearly, for the no-penalty approach, the generated foot contact sequence is periodic and maintains stable alternation throughout the entire period. For the fixed-penalty approach $\lambda E = -0.001$, the resulting rollout is shorter, and the foot contact sequence does not maintain regularity and stability in alternation towards the end of the episode. On the other hand, the recovery-aware approach ensures the consistency and

periodicity in footsteps throughout the whole 1000-step rollout.

Short-run hyperparameter sweeps were conducted as control experiments to validate that the main PPO algorithm ran in an acceptable range. Table 3 highlights the impact of learning rate, discount factor, and network size given limited training budgets.

Hyperparameter tuning
Learning-rate sweep

Learning rate	Steps alive (mean \pm std)	Return (mean \pm std)
1e-4	62.8 \pm 27.0	-1.498 \pm 1.033
2e-4	67.1 \pm 32.7	-1.410 \pm 1.060
3e-4	81.7 \pm 48.6	-1.056 \pm 1.586
5e-4	80.8 \pm 30.0	-1.253 \pm 1.089

Discount factor (γ) sweep

γ	Steps alive (mean \pm std)	Return (mean \pm std)
0.95	83.3 \pm 27.3	-1.253 \pm 0.418
0.97	77.4 \pm 19.4	-1.143 \pm 0.302
0.99	59.3 \pm 12.3	-1.235 \pm 0.285

Network architecture sweep (AUC summary at 20M)

MLP sizes	Last eval reward	Best eval reward	AUC avg
(256,128,64)	-2.449	-2.386	-3.102
(512,256,128)	-2.421	-2.346	-3.018
(1024,512,256)	-2.449	-2.354	-2.960

The hyperparameter sweeps were used as short-run control experiments rather than as the main contribution of the study. The learning-rate sweep showed that 3e-4 provided the best balance between survival and return among the tested values. The discount-factor sweep showed moderate variation across gamma values, with gamma = 0.97 providing the best return in the short-run setting. The network-architecture sweep showed similar final rewards across the tested MLP sizes, while the larger architecture achieved a slightly

better AUC at 20M steps. Overall, these sweeps served to verify that the baseline PPO settings were reasonable, while the main analysis focuses on the effect of fixed and recovery-aware energy regularization.

Finally, the MuJoCo-trained recovery-aware policy was transferred to PyBullet without additional learning. Figure 8 shows a typical zero-shot transfer performance of PyBullet from the MuJoCo-trained policy.

Figure 8: Sim-to-sim validation in PyBullet: a zero-shot rollout

A similar 29-DoF joint action mapping and PD control at the torque level were used. Key frames from the PyBullet rollout were saved for validation that (a) the robot shape remained the same (i.e., same URDF

for the Unitree G1 robot), and (b) the control rate structure was preserved (ctrl dt = 0.02 s with sim dt = 0.002 s or 10 Bullet substeps in every step). This validation also ensured that failures were not due to visualization

problems but actual instability in the environment. The performance of sim-to-sim was assessed by running the policy in PyBullet using the learned MuJoCo policy without any form of learning, and the survival time, traveled distance, and energy-related variables were recorded. In the zero-shot setting of PyBullet, the simulation was terminated after 151 control steps (3.02 seconds), with success = False, after covering 1.003 m before termination. The simulation ended because of instability, which was evidenced by an increase in actuation effort. The total actuation energy was 242,831.52 J, equivalent to an average power of 80,407.79 W over 3.02 seconds. With the total mass of 39.115 kg recorded in the experiment, the cost of transport (CoT) was 631.18. Therefore, the above variables define the sim-to-sim performance in terms of the magnitude of the mismatch under the strict setting of no retraining. In order to understand the cause of the premature termination of the sim-to-sim rollout, the base height and orientation were monitored during the execution in PyBullet. The rollout was initiated from a vertical position after the stabilization of the warm start, but it gradually lost stability in the initial few seconds, finally meeting the fall criteria. The $z(t)$ plot shows a rapid fall event with large roll and pitch angles. Therefore, the cause of the termination was a physical fall, not a command mismatch, since a zero command vector was used: $[0, 0, 0]$. This result confirms the hypothesis that the policy's stabilizing actions, learned from the MuJoCo physics environment, did not generalize to the PyBullet environment under the same high-level control interface. In order to contextualize the energy metrics reported in Table 2, the instantaneous actuation power and the total energy were computed from the joint torques and joint velocities during the PyBullet rollout. The power trace was found to have large peaks in the neighborhood of the termination event, leading to an overestimation of the mean power and total energy. The energy metrics (Energy, Mean Power, CoT) should thus be viewed in terms of instability due to simulation mismatch rather than efficiency in steady walking. This sim-to-sim analysis suggests that it is possible to use the MuJoCo Playground PPO policy in PyBullet with a correctly paired 29-DoF joint correspondence and control cadence without retraining. However, the performance drops significantly in the zero-shot case, resulting in termination at around 3 seconds with significant actuation effort. This is in accordance with expectations for simulator mismatch effects, in particular for contact and friction modeling and actuator/servo behavior. This suggests two possible avenues for future work: (i) presenting this performance degradation as a definitive sim-to-sim gap for zero-shot transfer, or (ii) using calibration methods (such as PD gain and torque limit alignment, inertial/friction matching, or domain randomization and fine-tuning) in subsequent experiments to reduce this gap. Overall, the results show that applying uniform fixed-energy penalization improves apparent efficiency only at the cost of reduced locomotion robustness. In particular, the ablation for the fixed-penalty scheme suggests that the choice of $\lambda E = -0.001$ can be considered as a baseline for the fixed-penalty regime since higher penalties led to poor survival rates.

In the main comparison, the fixed-penalty scheme decreased energy use but resulted in worse survival rates, travelled distances, and gait consistency compared to the recovery-aware regularization. Likewise, zero-shot transfer to rough terrain showed that the recovery-aware policy offered better locomotion robustness than fixed-energy penalization. Finally, the PyBullet sim-to-sim experiment illustrated that it is sufficient to apply the identical action mapping and control cycle time to guarantee executability but not for stable cross-simulator transfer.

Discussion

The primary contribution of the current research is that fixed-energy penalties lead to a direct trade-off between robustness and efficiency in the learning of humanoid locomotion, which is not seen for recovery-aware regularization. In the flat-terrain comparison, the method without any penalties stayed as the most reliable reference method, whereas the fixed-energy strategy with $\lambda E = -0.001$ decreased survival rates and gait reliability, yet was still trainable. The recovery-aware strategy partly compensated for the loss of robustness and maintained gait regularity, according to gait metrics and visual inspection. These findings indicate that the limitation of the energy penalty scheme does not depend on the scale of rewards but rather on when the penalty is introduced. Given that the same penalty applies in all iterations, the agent will be penalized from taking corrective measures to prevent falls, thus preventing the required activation that is necessary to recover balance and stability in the longer term. The recovery-aware scheme addresses this problem by loosening the penalty while the agent experiences an unstable state, then imposing it once again when the agent achieves stable locomotion. Therefore, the policy ensures that there is consistency with respect to the stepping pattern, less likelihood of slippage, and stability with regard to the torso. Domain shift results for zero-shot rough-terrain confirm the same interpretation. The no-penalty policy was the best condition concerning robustness of the transfer, while the fixed-penalty approach exhibited significantly reduced survival and reward. The recovery-aware approach helped recover from this decreased robustness, implying that stability-conditioned regularization transfers to rough-terrain disturbances better than applying a fixed-penalty. From this perspective, the proposed approach not only enhances walking on a flat terrain but also makes the walk more robust. The efficiency analysis offers a clearer perspective on the trade-off. The fixed-penalty lowered the average power and overall energy, but at the cost of a decreased survival and distance traveled, which means that some of the perceived benefits in terms of energy efficiency were obtained by restricting locomotion behavior. On the other hand, the recovery-aware strategy worked under a high energy consumption level but kept locomotion behavior sustained and more structured. This implies that, within the current context, the relevant question is not only the amount of energy to be penalized but rather when this punishment should occur within the movement. The sim-to-sim experiment in PyBullet offers an alternative angle of assessing robustness for practical application. While the policy trained on MuJoCo is runnable in PyBullet with equivalent

joint configuration, torque-based PD controller, and sampling frequency, the episode ended prematurely because of a physical fall. This finding implies that execution across different simulation environments does not ensure stability. The high level of effort expended near the end of the episode indicates that the stabilizing control behavior acquired from MuJoCo did not successfully translate to PyBullet physics. Therefore, the sim-to-sim outcome needs to be viewed as an indicator of the actual existence of the gap between simulators, rather than efficiency considerations. There are several limitations that must be mentioned. First, the gait metrics considered were taken as diagnostics of representative rollouts and not as distributions across multiple episodes. In addition, sim-to-sim transfer has been carried out in a zero-shot way, which means without calibrating or training again; while this method can show mismatches, it cannot specify the exact physical cause of the failure. Finally, the current analysis only involves joystick-trained walking and ignores any other aspects of task generalization abilities. This suggests that future work should consider two main directions. First, the recovery-aware method can be developed further toward more smooth, or even continuous stability-conditioned scheduling rather than an on/off switch approach. Secondly, the sim-to-sim technique can be developed further in the direction of PD gain adaptation, matching the friction and inertia, limiting the fine-tuning phase, and assessing the performance of the recovery-aware policy in PyBullet directly. All things considered, the current results point toward promising directions in humanoid locomotion where stability-conditioned energy regulation emerges as a valuable approach, especially when preserving robustness is the main concern.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study is to validate whether the reproducible RL framework of the Unitree G1 could be used to achieve both the ability to walk stably as a humanoid in simulation, as well as provide the necessary analysis regarding robustness and efficiency through energy regularization. With the help of MuJoCo Playground and PPO, different experiments have been performed using flat ground, zero-shot rough terrain transfer, and sim-to-sim execution in PyBullet. The findings indicate that fixed-energy penalties lead to a significant trade-off between robustness and efficiency. From among all the fixed-penalties evaluated, $\lambda E = -0.001$ was the only viable starting point for training, while the use of higher penalties decreased reward gains and survival. However, even this relatively low-level penalty led to poorer locomotion stability and gait consistency. Recovery-aware regularization kept a higher level of stability during walking, regularity of contact occurrence, and increased survival on both flat and rough terrains. The efficiency analysis demonstrated that decreased energy use due to the penalty was accomplished partially through restricting locomotion activities, while the recovery-aware policy allowed maintaining continuous motion through reducing penalty during unstable moments. The sim-to-sim experiment provides the strongest motivation for deployment-oriented evaluation, since the policy, trained on MuJoCo, is executable in PyBullet with the same 29-DOF action mapping, torque-level PD control, and control

cadence, but the zero-shot rollout is terminated within seconds with significant actuation effort. This result shows that compatibility is not guaranteed across simulators, and sim differences, especially regarding contact, friction, and actuation, may be critical. Hence, it is proposed to view the execution of the policy as separate from the stability of the policy. In summary, the findings indicate that stability-based energy regularization outperforms the traditional penalty approach for maintaining reliable humanoid locomotion. Further research needs to be conducted to incorporate the current study into a and calibration methods to minimize the discrepancy between different physics engines.

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